

Set Reconciliation With an Inaccurate Oracle

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I. INTRODUCTION

Abstract—In this work, we consider a variant of the set reconciliation problem where the estimate for the size of the symmetric difference may be inaccurate. Given this setup, we propose a new method to reconciling sets of data and we then compare our method to the Invertible Bloom Filter approach proposed by Eppstein et al. [2].

For the next ten years, one of the greatest challenges faced by the defense community will be developing new capabilities to handle big data. A driving force behind the proliferation of data in the Navy community is growing demand for intelligence, surveillance, and reconnaissance (ISR) data for enhanced situational awareness. As recently as 2014, it was estimated that less than 5% of data collected from ISR platforms reaches Navy analysts [9]. Often times, this problem is the result of low-bandwidth (or otherwise poor) communication links. Another common issue is duplicate data is transferred between many hosts [11]. In an effort to improve the flow of information across these links and prevent the transfer of data shared between collections of hosts, in this work we consider a variant of the *set reconciliation* problem.

The set reconciliation problem has the following setup. Suppose two hosts, A and B , each have a set of binary strings of length b . Let \mathcal{S}_A denote the set of strings on Host A and let \mathcal{S}_B denote the set of strings on Host B . The set reconciliation problem is to determine, using the minimum amount of information exchange, what to send from Host A to Host B with a single round of communication so that Host B can compute their symmetric difference $\mathcal{S}_A \triangle \mathcal{S}_B = (\mathcal{S}_A \setminus \mathcal{S}_B) \cup (\mathcal{S}_B \setminus \mathcal{S}_A)$ where $d = |\mathcal{S}_A \triangle \mathcal{S}_B|$ and M is an estimate for an upper bound on d . Under the traditional setup, the estimate on d is accurate so that $d \leq M$ always holds.

The set reconciliation problem has received considerable attention in the past. The work in [6] and [8] propose the use of algebraic error correction codes. The approach in [8], which we refer to as polynomial interpolation (PI), was shown to be nearly optimal with respect to the amount of information exchange. However, the primary drawback with PI is that it possesses high $O(M^3)$ computational complexity. Later works, such as [2] and [7], propose the use of structures similar to Bloom filters [4]. These schemes also achieve nearly optimal information exchange. Furthermore, the approaches in [2] and [4] exhibit lower computational complexity. In particular, the Invertible Bloom Filter (IBF) approach in [2] has computational complexity $O(M)$.

Many variations of the set reconciliation problem have been studied in the literature. In [7], the authors allow

multiple rounds of communication. [1] considers where small errors between elements of the data sets are handled differently than large discrepancies. [3] considers where elements in the symmetric difference are related.

In this work, we consider a new problem which, to the best of the authors' knowledge, has not been studied before. Classically, it is assumed that the estimate for the upper bound on d , which we denote as M , is accurate so that $d \leq M$ always holds. The aim of this work will be to consider where the oracle (estimate for d) is inaccurate so that it may be that $d > M$. Our contributions will be to propose a new algorithm, which we refer to as the Layered PI approach (or our approach when the context is clear), that is robust against an inaccurate oracle. We then compare our approach with IBF and demonstrate an improvement given the oracle is inaccurate.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the Layered PI approach. We then evaluate our approach in Section IV using the setup described in Section III. Finally, Section V concludes the paper.

II. LAYERED PI ALGORITHM

In this section, we describe the Layered PI algorithm. The idea is first to sub-divide the space $\{0, 1\}^b$ containing the data strings into random subsets and run PI on each of these smaller sets. Note that a similar approach was also used in [7]. In [7], the authors randomly partition the space $\{0, 1\}^b$ into subsets and ran PI on each subset to reduce the high computational complexity of PI, but they then allow multiple rounds of communication. We adopt a similar approach to enable partial recovery of the symmetric difference when $d > M$, but maintain only a single round of communication.

The Layered PI approach calls the encode and decode methods of PI algorithm of [8]. In executing PI, one encodes the data sets with a threshold parameter M . The value of M will be fixed at each layer of our algorithm. If $M \geq d$ then decoding will recover the entire symmetric difference. However, if $M < d$, then decoding may fail to recover anything (assuming that failure is detected). It is this value of M that determines the complexity of both the encode and decode of the PI algorithm; M 's relationship to d determines whether PI succeeds or fails. Given an oracle that provides the value of d , one would set $M = d$ and achieve the best possible complexity results. In our approach we will set the value of M and strategically run many instances of PI, expecting only some them to succeed.

Next we informally describe the encoding procedure performed on the sets \mathcal{S}_A and \mathcal{S}_B . We partition the space

\mathbb{F}_2^b into $\ell = \frac{d}{\log(d)}$ bins each containing $\frac{n}{\ell}$ strings. Then, we perform PI on each bin, meaning we compute ℓ characteristic functions (one for each bin), and evaluate each function at the same threshold of M points. In addition, we compute a hash consisting of H bits for each bin. Next, we similarly re-partition space into another set of ℓ bins each of size $\frac{n}{\ell}$. We again compute the characteristic function for each bin, except that now each characteristic function is evaluated at fM points and we compute a hash of fH bits for each bin, where $0 < f < 1$. This process is iterated each time with a new partitioning scheme except the number of evaluation points and the length of the hashes are reduced by a factor of f each iteration until the number of evaluation points is less than or equal to $\log(\log(d))$. We transmit the outcome of ALL the evaluations along with ALL the hashes to Host B, in a single transmit.

Fig. 1: Example of algorithm, 2 layers partitioning into 3 bins. In layer 1, one bin fails to decode since it has 3 “balls,” exceeding the encode threshold $M = 2$. In layer 2, one bin would fail if not for the modify procedure which removed a ball decoded in an earlier layer.

We now more formally describe the encoding process, followed the decoding procedure. The input to the procedure below is the set $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathbb{F}_2^b$. Let $\chi_{\mathcal{S}}(z) = \prod_{x \in \mathcal{S}} (z - x) \in \mathbb{F}_q[z]$ be a univariate polynomial with the indeterminate z , where there is an injective mapping of length- b bitstrings onto elements of the field \mathbb{F}_q and $q \geq 2^b$, also known as the characteristic polynomial of the set \mathcal{S} . Let h_k be a hash which takes as input a subset of \mathbb{F}_2^b and outputs $[k]$ bits. Let $K = \lceil \log \log(d) \rceil$ and suppose we have the subsets $\mathcal{U}_{1,1}, \mathcal{U}_{1,2}, \dots, \mathcal{U}_{1,\ell}, \mathcal{U}_{2,1}, \mathcal{U}_{2,2}, \dots, \mathcal{U}_{2,\ell}, \dots, \mathcal{U}_{K+1,1}, \mathcal{U}_{K+1,2}, \dots, \mathcal{U}_{K+1,\ell}$ where for any $i \in [K+1]$, $\mathcal{U}_{i,1}, \mathcal{U}_{i,2}, \dots, \mathcal{U}_{i,\ell}$ is a partition of the space \mathbb{F}_2^b . For shorthand, let $\mathcal{S}(i, j)$ denote the elements of $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathbb{F}_2^b$ that are in $\mathcal{U}_{i,j}$. Here we have that $\mathcal{S}(i, j)$ refers to bin j at layer i . Let c_1, c_2 (discussed later) be such that $0 < c_1 < 1 < c_2$. For $i \in [K]$ let $E_i = \{e_{i,1}, e_{i,2}, \dots, e_{i,|E_i|}\} \subseteq \mathbb{F}_q$ such that $|E_i| = \lfloor (f)^{i-1} \cdot c_2 \log(d) \rfloor$, denote a set of evaluation points for characteristic polynomials with index i . Further ensure the evaluation points in E_i do not include any elements of \mathbb{F}_q mapped to by length- b bitstrings.

Similarly define E_{K+1} such that $|E_{K+1}| = \lfloor \log(d) \rfloor$. Let $H = \lfloor c_3 \log d \rfloor b$ for some $c_3 > 0$.

We first perform the encode operation, shown below, on both Host A and Host B.

Algorithm 1 Encode

Input: $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathbb{F}_2^b, E_i, H$

- 1: **for** $i \in [K]$ and $j \in [\ell]$ **do**
- 2: Compute $\chi_{\mathcal{S}(i,j)}(z), h^{i,j} = h_{\lfloor (f)^{i-1} H \rfloor}(\mathcal{S}(i, j))$.
- 3: Evaluate $\{\chi_{\mathcal{S}(i,j)}(e) | e \in E_i\} = \chi^{i,j}$.
- 4: **end for**
- 5: **for** $j \in [\ell]$ **do**
- 6: Compute $\chi_{\mathcal{S}(K+1,j)}(z)$.
- 7: Evaluate $\{\chi_{\mathcal{S}(K+1,j)}(e) | e \in E_{K+1}\} = \chi^{K+1,j}$.
- 8: **end for**

Output: $\chi^{i,j}, h^{i,j}, \chi^{K+1,j}$ for $i \in [K]$ and $j \in [\ell]$

Let $\chi_A^{i,j}, h_A^{i,j}, \chi_A^{K+1,j}$ and $\chi_B^{i,j}, h_B^{i,j}, \chi_B^{K+1,j}$ be the results of performing Encode on Host A and B, respectively. First, Host A sends $\chi_A^{i,j}, h_A^{i,j}, \chi_A^{K+1,j}$ for $i \in [K]$ and $j \in [\ell]$. Since $\chi^{i,j}$ requires $f^{i-1} \cdot c_2 \log(d) \cdot b$ bits of storage, $h^{i,j}$ requires $f^{i-1} \cdot c_3 \log(d) \cdot b$ bits of storage, and PI requires db bits of information exchange, notice that this requires at most

$$\sum_{i=0}^K (f)^i \cdot (c_2 \log(d) + c_3 \log(d)) b \cdot \frac{d}{\log(d)} + \log(d) \frac{d}{\log(d)} b \leq \frac{1}{1-f} (c_2 + c_3) db + db = O(db)$$

bits of information exchange. Similarly, as PI has encode complexity $O(d)$, our encode complexity is $O(d)$.

The ability to modify an already encoded $\chi_S^{i,j}$ to add or remove elements is possible in linear time [8] and it is shown below as Algorithm 2. D_1, D_2 will designate the sets of elements we want to add, remove respectively.

Algorithm 2 Modify

Input: $D_1, D_2 \subseteq \mathcal{S}(i, j)$ such that $D_1 \cap D_2 = \emptyset, \chi_S^{i,j}, E_i$

- 1: Compute $\frac{\chi_{D_1}(z)}{\chi_{D_2}(z)} = \chi_{D_1, D_2}^*(z)$
- 2: Evaluate $\{\chi_{\mathcal{S}(i,j)}(e) \cdot \chi_{D_1, D_2}^*(e) | e \in E_i\} = \chi_{\mathcal{S} \Delta D}^{i,j}$

Output: $\chi_{\mathcal{S} \Delta D}^{i,j}$

Let $\text{PID}(\chi_{S_1}, \chi_{S_2}, E), E \subseteq \mathbb{F}_q$ denote the standard PI decode algorithm, where E is the evaluation set and $|E| = M$; recall that it outputs $S_1 \Delta S_2$ if $|S_1 \Delta S_2| \leq M$ the threshold at which the two χ 's were originally encoded [8]. Using Algorithm 2, we can potentially decrease the symmetric difference between the encoded sets and thus improve the likelihood for PID to successfully decode given knowledge of some of the elements in the symmetric difference. We now present in Algorithm 3 the decode algorithm which is performed on Host B, which calls the modify algorithm discussed earlier.

Recall that PI has decode complexity $O(M^3)$. Thus

Algorithm 3 Decode

Input: $\chi_A^{i,j}, h_A^{i,j}, \chi_A^{K+1,j}, \chi_B^{i,j}, \chi_B^{K+1,j}, \mathcal{S}_B, |E_i|$

- 1: Initialize $\mathcal{D} = \emptyset$.
- 2: **for** $i \leftarrow 1$ to $K + 1$ **do**
- 3: Compute $D_1 = \mathcal{D} \cap \mathcal{S}_B, D_2 = \mathcal{D} \setminus \mathcal{S}_B$
- 4: **for** $j \leftarrow 1$ to ℓ **do**
- 5: Compute $\chi_{A\Delta D}^{i,j} =$
 Modify($D_1(i, j), D_2(i, j), \chi_A^{i,j}, E_i$)
- 6: Compute $D' = \text{PID}(\chi_{A\Delta D}^{i,j}, \chi_B^{i,j}, E_i)$
- 7: **if** $i = K + 1$ **or** $h_{f^{i-1}H}(\mathcal{S}_B(i, j)\Delta(\mathcal{D} \cup D')) = h_A^{i,j}$ **then**
- 8: Update $\mathcal{D} = \mathcal{D} \cup D'$.
- 9: **end if**
- 10: **end for**
- 11: **end for**

Output: \mathcal{D}

our algorithm has decode complexity $O(d \cdot \log(d)^2)$:

$$\sum_{i=0}^K f^i \left([c_2 \log(d)]^3 + c_3 \log(d) \right) \frac{d}{\log(d)} + \frac{d}{\log(d)}.$$

$$\log(d)^3 = O(d \cdot \log(d)^2).$$

In the following, we discuss the intuition behind our approach. Since we partitioned the universe (of size $n = 2^b$) into ℓ random bins, if there are d elements in the symmetric difference, then each bin is expected to contain $d \cdot \frac{\log(d)}{d} = \log(d)$ elements from the symmetric difference as it follows a binomial distribution $B(N, p)$ where $N = \frac{n \cdot \log(d)}{d}$ and $p = \frac{d}{n}$. The variance is $\frac{n \cdot \log(d)}{d} \cdot \frac{d}{n} \cdot (1 - \frac{d}{n}) < \log(d)$, and thus $\sigma < \sqrt{\log(d)}$. Thus for any fixed $0 < c_1 < 1 < c_2$, for large enough d at least half of the total bins will contain between $c_1 M$ and $c_2 M$ elements from the set difference. Using PI, we can recover at least $(\frac{1}{2}l)(c_4 M) > 0$ elements for some $c_4 > 0$, or a fixed positive fraction of the total symmetric difference. Iterating, we can recover at least that same fraction of the remaining symmetric difference each layer until almost all the elements in the symmetric difference have been recovered. Under certain conditions, the $K+1$ layer then has sufficiently high threshold to recover the rest.

The following theorem shows that for large d (and correspondingly large $n = 2^b$, as trivially $n \geq 2d$) that the probability of our algorithm successfully recovering the symmetric difference tends to 1. The proof is a straightforward application of Chernoff bounds. While our earlier treatment of our algorithm dealt with general parameters, for the below theorem we chose the following fixed values to simplify our proof: $c_1 = 1/3$, $c_2 = 7/4$, $c_3 = 1/4$, $f = 1/6$.

Theorem 1. Suppose $n = 2^b \geq 2d$ and $d \geq 1024$. Let $\mathcal{S}_A, \mathcal{S}_B \subseteq \mathbb{F}_2^b$ where for any $x \in \mathbb{F}_2^b$, $Pr(x \in \mathcal{S}_A \Delta \mathcal{S}_B) = \frac{d}{n}$. Then the probability the algorithm fails to recover the symmetric difference, denoted $Pr(F)$, is

at most

$$Pr(F) \leq \log \log d \left(2(0.999)^{\left(\frac{3}{4}\right)^{\log d} \cdot \frac{d}{\log d}} + 2^{-\frac{b}{4} \cdot \log(d)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right)$$

so that $Pr(F) \rightarrow 0$, as $d \rightarrow \infty$.

The above discussion forms the theoretical basis for our algorithm, but a number of parameters are up for selection in implementation. Next we motivate our selection of these parameters and define our implementation.

The full algorithm has multiple layers. In a given layer, we want M to be small and l to be large, since each call of PID has complexity $O(M^3)$. In choosing l to be roughly $d/\log(d)$, we expect roughly $\log(d)$ elements of the symmetric difference per bin at the first layer. While the distribution of this balls and bins problem means that some bins will have more balls than $\log(d)$, by setting M at slightly above that value, we expect a reasonable number of bins to successfully decode. Moreover, we expect a reasonable number of elements of the symmetric difference to be in successfully decoded bins. If we adjust M appropriately from layer to layer, we can maintain a set fractional decoding in every layer – our goal is half.

Initial values of M, l, K are determined by a Heuristic, as is the value of M at each layer. Pseudocode for our implementation and both Heuristics are below.

Algorithm 4 Simulation Implementation

Input: $\mathcal{S}_A, \mathcal{S}_B, d$

- 1: $M_1, l, K \leftarrow \text{Heuristic}_1(d)$
- 2: **for** $i \leftarrow 1$ to K **do**
- 3: **for all** $x \in \mathbb{F}_2^b$ **do**
- 4: Assign x to $\mathcal{U}_{i,j}$ uniformly at random, $j \in [1, l]$
- 5: **end for**
- 6: Pick E_i such that $|E_i| = M_i$
- 7: $M_{i+1} \leftarrow \text{Heuristic}_2(M_i)$
- 8: **end for**
- 9: $E_{K+1} \leftarrow \emptyset$
- 10: $\chi_A^{i,j}, h_A^{i,j}, \chi_A^{K+1,j} \leftarrow \text{Encode}(\mathcal{S}_A, E_i, H)$
- 11: $\chi_B^{i,j}, h_B^{i,j}, \chi_B^{K+1,j} \leftarrow \text{Encode}(\mathcal{S}_B, E_i, H)$
- 12: $\mathcal{D} \leftarrow \text{Decode}(\chi_A^{i,j}, h_A^{i,j}, \emptyset, \chi_B^{i,j}, \emptyset, \mathcal{S}_B, |E_i|)$

Output: \mathcal{D}

Algorithm 5 Heuristic₁

Input: d

- 1: **if** $d \leq 3$ **then**
- 2: $d \leftarrow 3 + 1$
- 3: **end if**
- 4: $M \leftarrow \lceil \log_3(d) \rceil$
- 5: $l \leftarrow \lceil \frac{d}{\log_3(d)} \rceil$
- 6: $K \leftarrow \lceil \log_2(M) \rceil$
- 7: **if** $K = 1$ **then**
- 8: $M \leftarrow M + 1$
- 9: **end if**

Output: M, l, K

Algorithm 6 Heuristic₂**Input:** M 1: $M \leftarrow \lceil M/2 \rceil + 1$ **Output:** M

Our goal was to decode at least half of the elements in each layer – and our simulation results show we met (and usually far exceeded) that goal in almost every run. Thus, we decreased the value of M by roughly half each layer until it hit 1 which means $K \sim \log \log d$. In practice K will be very small, ≤ 3 in all cases we considered.

Thus we developed our two Heuristics to compensate for the small number of layers. Heuristic₁ targets especially small values of d which would only have a single layer. Heuristic₂ considers cases where there are multiple layers. In both cases we slightly boost M in order to provide faster convergence, since K is small. In simulation, the algorithm was already fairly successful at decoding, so we chose to skip the $K + 1$ layer. In Algorithm 4 we denote this by letting $|E_{K+1}| = 0$ so the encoding in layer $K + 1$ would be empty and we explicitly enter \emptyset into the $K + 1$ 'th layer's inputs for Decode.

III. SIMULATION

To test our algorithm, we generated synthetic data and had our algorithm attempt to find the symmetric difference while recording certain metrics to gauge performance. We tracked the fraction of the symmetric difference that successfully decoded at the end of each layer, as well as cost of space to transmit and decode computation. We then ran IBF against the exact same synthetic data sets, with the same amount of space.

A. Synthetic Data

The universe Ω of possible set elements is of size $|\Omega| = 10000$. The set \mathcal{S}_A is of size $|\mathcal{S}_A| = 3000$, and was chosen uniformly at random from Ω . The size of the symmetric difference between \mathcal{S}_A and \mathcal{S}_B , d is the parameter we varied, from 1...1000. \mathcal{S}_B was constructed by modifying \mathcal{S}_A to achieve d . For each value of d , we ran the simulation $R = 10000$ times.

B. PI Implementation and Performance

For PI, successful decoding means the entire symmetric difference is recovered. Failure means potentially nothing is recovered. Recall decoding has $O(M^3)$ complexity; to save processing time, we implemented a blackbox that has total success/failure based on symmetric difference versus threshold.

The nuance is that when PI fails you need to detect the failure. Within the paper [8], they include additional evaluation points specifically to detect failure. This increase of the threshold above M impacts the complexity of encode, decode, and space requirements. The underlying assumption is this increase is small compared to M . In our approach, we try to keep M as small as possible, so this method will have a dramatic effect.

In contrast to [8], we utilize an independent hash function of size H . This changes the space required to $M \cdot b + H$, and probability of not detecting failure to 2^{-H} . We use $H = 10$ for all layers, which impacts the space required by our algorithm. We still assume our blackbox has a perfect ability to detect failure.

C. IBF Parameters

For the IBF algorithm, we used the implementation of Invertible Bloom Lookup Table (IBLT) from [12]. IBLT is more general than IBF in that it encodes a key-value pair [4]. By encoding just the key, you get an IBF.

An IBF consists of m of cells, each tracking three values: count, sum of IDs, and sum of hash of IDs. As parameters for the IBF, one needs to choose m , as well as how much space to allocate to the count and each of the two sums, and k how many different cells each element gets hashed to. In practice $k = 3$ or 4 usually works well [2], so we chose $k = 3$. The IDs are the binary representation of elements in Ω and hence require b space; and the hash permutes elements of Ω . Binary XOR sums of such values require b space.

If N is the number of elements, $\frac{Nk}{m}$ is expected number of elements that get hashed to a given cell. We assign count $c = \lceil \log_2(\frac{Nk}{m}) \rceil + 1$ bits of space. Thus each cell uses $2b + c$ bits of space, making the total space used by the IBF algorithm $m(2b + c)$. Let P be the bits of space used by the PI based Algorithm 4. We choose $m = \lceil \frac{P}{m(2b+c)} \rceil$. Since c and m depend on each other, we iteratively update them based on these formulas until they reach a stable point. Further we force $c \geq 2$. Thus the amount of space used by IBF will be $\geq P$.

D. Second Simulation

We ran a second simulation where we fixed the amount of space allowed (as if $d = 50$) but changed the true value of d . We used $|\Omega| = 1000$, $|\mathcal{S}_A| = |\mathcal{S}_B| = 300$, $R = 1000$ and we ran the simulation across $d = 40...130$. The purpose was to investigate how resilient both algorithms were when the estimate for symmetric difference was incorrect.

IV. RESULTS

Figure 2a shows that the space requirement of Algorithm 4 increases roughly linearly, with jumps due to the ceiling functions. Figure 2b shows compute time for decode increases faster than linearly, but notably is less than cubic. Figures 2c, 2d show the distribution of results for two example values of d , 18 and 675 respectively. More specifically they show fraction of the symmetric difference that was successfully recovered at the end of a run, tallying over 10,000 runs, and displaying that distribution for both algorithms. These values of d were chosen as they showcased examples where Algorithm 4 had relatively more runs fail to fully decode and thus resulted in more interesting distributions.

Figures 2e, 2f, 2g compare Algorithm 4's performance to IBF's across $d = 1...1000$. In Figure 2e, we tally the

Fig. 2: (a)-(j) measure different performance metrics between Algorithm 4 (Alg) and IBF. The specifics are detailed in the text of the Results section.

number of runs that successfully decoded the entire symmetric difference. Note the large spikes correspond to the small jumps in space used. In Figures 2f, 2g, we count the fraction of symmetric difference that successfully decoded averaged across certain runs – respectively over all runs and excluding runs that were 100% successful (if all runs are excluded, the average set to 1).

Figures 2h, 2i, 2j show the results of the second simulation where the space used by both algorithms was fixed and we varied the value of $d = 40 \dots 130$. Recall this simulation had 1000 runs per value of d . Figure 2h tallies the number of runs that successfully decode the entire symmetric difference. Figures 2i, 2j show the fraction of the symmetric difference decoded averaged over all runs and excluding 100% successful runs, respectively.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Layered PI has several desirable characteristics, particularly from the perspective of Disconnected Intermittent Limited (DIL) environments. Given the same space, our algorithm fully decodes the symmetric difference on average better than IBF as seen in Figure 2e. However,

we feel the more compelling story comes from examining what happens when the symmetric difference is not fully decoded. In that case, our algorithm successfully decodes a very high fraction of the symmetric difference, while IBF performance is notably lower. Figures 2f, 2g make the comparison across different values of d ; note that our algorithm’s performance is usually in the high 90%’s. Figures 2c, 2d showcase the distributions in more detail for $d = 18$ and 675 respectively. And while both algorithms operate with a single round of communication, if the decode is not fully successful, our algorithm still manages to recover most of that symmetric difference. This has significant implications if a subsequent round of communication is not possible, and even if it is, it lightens the load for that next round.

In practice, one does not know the exact size of the symmetric difference a priori and must use another technique to estimate its value. PI is extremely sensitive to that estimate. IBF of course is more resilient than PI, but our results show that the layered PI approach with our algorithm outperforms IBF in this regard. In our second simulation we fixed the space allotted for both algorithms as if $d = 50$, but then let the actual d vary from 40...130. Performance of the algorithms were captured in Figures 2h, 2i, 2j and notably show our algorithm to the right of IBF by about 10 – 20 values of d .

The price our algorithm pays for these advantages comes from space required and decode complexity. Recall that PI and IBF require db and $O(db)$ space respectively while our algorithm requires $O(db)$. All share an encode complexity of $O(d)$. Decode complexity for PI and IBF are $O(d^3)$ and $O(d)$ respectively while for our algorithm it is $O(d \cdot \log(d)^2)$. However, decoding for our algorithm can be performed in parallel across $\ell = \frac{d}{\log d}$ nodes, and reaggregating the results gives an effective decode complexity of $O(d)$ after parallelization thus reducing the gap between IBF and our approach.

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